

Gene epistasis influences metabolism of *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*

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Abstract

Epistasis, the interaction of genes in a non-additive manner is crucial for understanding changes in gene expression. By using public data from yeast metabolic mutants we explored the effect of epistasis in metabolism. By employing additive models as a null hypothesis, we analyzed differential gene expression in double mutants compared to single mutants and wild-type strains to isolate epistatic interactions. Specifically, we focused on genes differentially expressed in HL double mutants, which were not explained by single mutants H or L. Our analyses, which integrated metabolomics, proteomics, and transcriptomics data, identified a set of candidate genes affected by epistatic interactions. These genes were characterized through protein-protein interaction networks and gene regulatory networks, revealing notable correlations and structural differences at the proteomics level. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Partial Least Squares (PLS) indicated variable reproducibility in metabolomics data, but a strong explanatory power for epistatic genes relative to the transcriptome.

Introduction

Epistasis is a phenomenon described as the alteration of the genotype by the interaction of different genes in a non-additive manner. It requires to be studied in detail to explain multiple biological systems of interest to researchers. Detection of epistatic mechanisms requires perspectives from various 'omics data like metabolomics, transcriptomics and proteomics (Pedruzzi *et al.* 2018). In the Alam *et al.* (2016) paper, 15 auxotrophic mutants of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were used to create additive and multiplicative models to explain the epistatic mechanisms. As these are determinants of gene expression, metabolic mutants can give an idea of gene regulation when responsive to nutrient availability (Alam *et al.*, 2016).

Our objective was to explore the epistasis phenomenon using a subset of the data provided from the paper using the H, L, prototroph and HL double mutant. We decided to use an additive model as a null to study epistasis. Under that model, the differential expression of a double mutant can be explained by the addition of each mutant and an interaction term that represents epistatic

genes. Using a system with one double mutant, the respective single mutants and a wild type strain it is possible to characterize epistatic genes. We were interested in looking at which genes are differentially expressed in HL compared to the prototroph and studying their metabolic and transcriptional interactions. This would be subtracted from genes differentially expressed in H compared to the prototroph and L compared to the prototroph to only focus only on genes differentially expressed in HL that cannot be explained by the response of the single mutants. Diverse mutants were used in our studies to get a better picture of how different genes interact and explore how they contribute to the phenomenon of epistasis.

Materials and Methods

Differential expression analysis

To start with our analysis, we performed a differential expression test using the DESeq2 package in R (Love *et al.* 2014). We used all three replicates for the genotypes H, L, HL and WT and we applied all the filtering used in Alam *et al.* (2016), which discarded transcripts with less than 50 counts across replicates. The model implemented was dependent of the genotype and all the contrasts were calculated to obtain adjusted p-values and log2 fold changes for pairwise comparisons. To be able to identify the set of epistatic genes we used the following formula:

$$\text{Epistatic_genes} = \text{DE(HL vs WT)} - \text{DE(H vs WT)} - \text{DE(L vs WT)}$$

To filter out differentially expressed genes in each genotype we used an adjusted p-value of 0.05, a log2 fold change value of 0.05 for underexpression and 2 for overexpression.

Gene Regulatory Network

In order to look at which transcription factors are regulating these genes, a gene regulatory network was created. The transcription factors were selected from the transcriptomics expression data provided. For creating the gene regulatory networks, GENIE3 R package was used because it showed better performance than other current methods such as CLR, ARACHNE (Huynh-Thu *et al.* 2019) and also performed the best in the DREAM4 challenge in predicting the regulators. It can also predict directed networks which no current approach which depends on mutual information or correlation can do. The expression matrix was created where the rows are the unique IDs of the genes and the columns are the expression counts of the samples, in our case the mutants. The list of transcription factors selected were then given as regulators for running GENIE3. It outputs a weight matrix which is an adjacency matrix where the rows are the transcription factors and the columns are all the genes. Each weight $[i, j]$ represents the weight of the link directed from i^{th} gene to j^{th} gene. GENIE3 also generated a link list which had the regulators and the potential targets followed by the weight designated to each regulator-target link. A threshold for the weight can be set to filter out any regulator-target links which have a lower weight assigned to them. The regulators that we obtained were then tested for enrichment against the epistatic genes to see how many of them are targeted by these TFs. A hypergeometric test was performed to test the significance of this enrichment. Since there were many p-values generated, we applied the Bonferroni-Hochberg p-value correction to test for the significance of the enrichment.

Protein-protein Interaction (PPI) Networks

To further characterize the set of epistatic genes from this study we used PPI networks. Data from experimentally validated PPI was downloaded from the BIOGRID database (Stark *et al.*, 2005). Interactions were filtered to only interactions from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (ORGANISM_B_ID==559292). This table was converted into a network using igraph and simplified for further analysis, removing multiple and duplicate edges. The resulting network was subsetted first using the epistatic genes and then using proteomics data, using spearman correlation coefficient and the three replicates for the H, L, HL and WT genotypes. Distribution of the spearman correlation was plotted and the epistatic proteins were compared to the rest of the proteome, taking as a random distribution the permutation of the dataset.

Analysis of centrality for the epistatic proteins as compared to the whole proteome was calculated, to check what was found in the reference paper. Clusters were computed and functionally annotated using GO terms. Finally we computed graphlets on the final subnetwork, using the proteomics correlation data as weight. Analyses and visualizations were done with the igraph package in R (Csardi & Nepusz, 2006).

GO enrichment analysis

We used the ClusterProfiler package in R (Yu *et al.* 2012) to do GO enrichment analysis for the clusters obtained from the gene regulatory and protein-protein interaction networks. To start we installed the *S. cerevisiae* GO database library(org.Sc.sgd.db) and each cluster was analysed using all the transcriptome as the universe. Biological Process “BP” ontologies were calculated, using the Benjamini-Hochberg adjusting method and cutoffs of 0.01 for p-value and 0.05 for q-value. In the case of GRN clusters, we calculated the ontologies for the targets of the top ranked transcription factors based on their enrichment in epistatic genes. For PPI networks the clusters were calculated based on degree and edge weight as it was explained previously.

PCA and PLS analysis to integrate metabolomics data

In order to correlate metabolomics and transcriptomics data we integrated the datasets using PCA and PLS. We filtered out duplicate metabolites and metabolites with zero variance before running the analysis and we kept the same structure from the replicates for each genotype (three replicates each). The analysis was run using the code provided in class. Two types of analyses were done, one with the whole transcriptome and another one with only the epistatic genes. Both analyses were compared to identify how much variation in the metabolites can be explained by the set of candidate epistatic genes and how that relates to our previous results.

A general summary of methods can be found in figure 1.

Figure 1. The general workflow implemented.

Results and Discussion

Differential expression allowed us to propose epistatic genes

Figure 2 shows some visualization of this analysis with volcano plots for each comparison and a PCA plot of the samples. This result reiterated what was shown in the paper - H mutant and prototroph clustered closer to each other away from where the L and HL mutants clustered together. Both the PCA and by the number of differentially expressed genes in the H vs WT contrast showed the similarity between these samples, only having 2 differentially expressed genes in the contrast.

After applying the additive model the epistatic genes were calculated as described in the methods section. A total of 531 genes were found to be uniquely differentially expressed in the HL mutant and not in either of the single mutants H and L. Under our hypothesis that the genes that cannot be explained using the additive model will be considered epistatic, these 531 genes represent the set used in our study for further analysis.

Figure 2. (A-C) Volcano plots for the differential expression analysis of the mutants HL, H, L vs WT yeast strain. (D) PCA plot of the samples.

Gene Regulatory Networks identified transcription factors involved in epistasis

We got a total of 154 genes which were 'Transcription Factors' from the transcriptomics data that was provided. GENIE3 was then run using two different stringencies - one in which the 154 transcription factors were provided as 'regulators' and the other with the epistatic genes also as 'targets'. For the first run of GENIE3, we tested for the enrichment of the epistatic genes in the targets of the generated network. We also calculated the total number of targets and then calculated the hypergeometric p-value and some of the GO enrichment terms for those genes.

Table 1 and 2 show the top 7 of the transcription factors and a summary of the results. Clusterprofiler was used to find enrichment of annotation for these 7 transcription factor genes.

Transcription Factors	Frequency in DE genes	TF targets	Hypergeometric test p-value	GO enriched annotation
YLR183C	374	1573	1.11e-138	translation, peptide biosynthesis and metabolism, ribosome biogenesis and assembly
YJL056C	354	1619	1.79e-114	peptide metabolism and biosynthesis, mitochondrial gene expression
YMR270C	359	1720	6.57e-110	spindle pole body organization, microtubule-based process
YNL216W	338	1590	1.16e-102	mitochondrial and cytoplasmic translation, microtubule organizing center organization
YJL168C	356	1778	2.81e-102	positive regulation of cellular component organization, microtubule cytoskeleton organization
YOR066W	338	1674	1.84e-95	mitochondrial and cytoplasmic translation, sister chromatin biorientation
YOR110W	380	2180	4.21e-92	positive regulation of cell cycle process, mitochondrial gene expression

Table 1. Seven of the top transcription factors selected as regulators, with enrichment in the epistatic genes, a hypergeometric test adjusted p-value and the GO enrichment terms.

Transcription Factor	Information from Transcriptomics data
YLR183C	putative transcription factor, contains Forkhead Associated domain
YJL056C	zinc-regulated transcription factor
YMR270C	protein involved in promoting high level transcription of rDNA
YNL216W	essential DNA-binding transcription regulator that binds many loci
YJL168C	histone methyltransferase with a role in transcriptional elongation
YOR066W	activator of G1-specific transcription factors MBF and SBF
YOR110W	essential subunit of RNA polymerase III transcription factor (TFIIIB)

Table 2. Information about the seven transcription factors from the transcriptomics data provided

Figure 3. GO enrichment terms for targets of TFs (A) 'YLR183C' and (B) 'YJL056C'.

This analysis allowed us to identify regulators of the epistatic genes, proposing a mechanism of action of the differences in the expression of the HL mutant as compared to the single mutants. These transcription factors had a high enrichment in predicted targets with the epistatic genes, therefore they represent an excellent group for functional validation and better understanding of the epistasis in this system.

Protein-protein Interaction Networks indicate specific characteristics for epistatic genes

We recovered a PPI network for *S. cerevisiae* from BIOGRID with 6082 nodes and 412952 edges. This initial network was characterized using centrality and betweenness and subsetted using the

epistatic genes. Figure 4 shows the $\log(\text{degree})$ distribution for each group, including the total number of proteins in the interactome, the epistatic genes as a subset, a random sample with the same size and the epistatic genes recalculating the centrality for only that group. We could not observe differences in the degrees for this set of predicted epistatic genes as compared to the whole interactome neither the random set. The reported behavior from the paper indicated that epistatic genes had less number of interactions that can lead to be more vulnerable to perturbations in the system. Our analysis did not show this, but maybe it is a subset of these epistatic genes which show this pattern.

Figure 4. $\log(\text{degree})$ distribution of the interactions from the PPI network for the total number of genes, the epistatic genes and a random sample of the same size.

To explore this idea we clustered the subnetwork and plotted the $\log(\text{degree})$ of each of the clusters (figure 5). We found some sub-structures of the $\log(\text{degree})$ in the clusters, specially for cluster number 4, 7 and 8. This indicates that there are clusters with less robustness, which can be susceptible to alterations, however this is not a general tendency in our group of epistatic genes, which differs to what was found in the paper.

Figure 5. Epistatic gene clusters in the PPI network and centrality calculations. Vertex color matches density colors for $\log(\text{degree})$.

Our next step was to generate a subnetwork with the epistatic genes only, and characterize it further using the proteomics dataset. We calculated pairwise spearman correlation coefficients using the proteomics dataset and weighted the edges with the rescaled results (zero to 1). Since the proteomics data is smaller than transcriptomics, after this subsetting we ended up with a network with 85 nodes and 253 edges. To test the significance of the raw correlations we performed a permutation test using 3000 iterations. The results are shown in figure 6. The

distributions show how the epistatic genes are more correlated than the expected by chance, having a majority of interactions weighted between 0.5 and 1. Even in the case when it is compared to the correlation of the whole proteome dataset we could observe a higher proportion of epistatic genes with larger correlation values. We interpret this result as evidence for a cohesive group of epistatic genes with similar behavior and common regulators, as it was analyzed using GRNs.

Figure 6. Proteomics correlation data in the context of the Yeast interactome. Plots for the epistatic genes in the interactome, the permuted distribution and the whole proteome.

We used this information to calculate clusters in the subnetwork using igraph, taking the weight as a parameter, and then we studied those clusters using GO analysis. Figure 7 contains a visualization for the clusters and some of the GO enrichment terms in these clusters. We found interesting groups enriched in activities as peptide metabolism, lipid metabolism and protein modification. These processes are highly correlated with the type of mutants we are studying in the project, and give us clues on how the cell metabolism is affected, taking us a step closer to the correlation with the phenotype.

Figure 7. Proteomics correlated PPI subnetwork and GO enrichment analysis

We also calculated the graphlets in the subnetwork to see the complexity of correlated subgraphs. From this analysis we found 249 graphlets, 141 with two nodes, 85 with three, 22 with four and 1 with five nodes. The big majority of the graphlets had only 2 nodes showing a low complexity. When we analysed the graphlets with higher number of nodes we identified that those were restricted to clusters 1 and 2, as we exemplify in figure 8. This is important since we found that cluster 2 is enriched in protein translation, indicating that functionally this cluster contain a higher complexity of interactions. We interpret this as that protein translation process requires a coalescence of several proteins to be achieved, and epistatic proteins play an important role in it which should be explored further using functional analysis.

Figure 8. Example of graphlets from the epistatic subnetwork, subsetted by proteomics correlation data. (A-D) Graphlets with 2, 3, 4 and 5 nodes were found.

We also determined central genes in this subnetwork, reported in table 3. These results sum to the current evidence for genes involved in protein and lipid metabolism as changes in chromatin state, another important process that regulates gene expression. The next logical step in our analysis was then to correlate the metabolomics data with what we have found so far, so we decided to take the transcriptomics and make a PCA/PLS analysis with the metabolomics data.

Node	Degree	Betweenness	Hub_score	Name	GO enrichment
YDR190C	31	814.0994	0.840527	ATP-dependent DNA helicase, also known as pontin	
YOR362C	21	238.5799	1	Alpha 7 subunit of the 20S proteasome	protein degradation
YIL133C	20	413.9998	0.368068	Ribosomal 60S subunit protein L16A	peptide biosynthetic process
YBR160W	18	278.7428	0.6631	Cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK) catalytic subunit	
YBR009C	16	58.05531	0.695356	Histone H4	DNA conformation change
YDL100C	16	112.293	0.703901	Guanine nucleotide exchange factor for Gpa1p	protein degradation
YML008C	16	196.2258	0.432028	Delta(24)-sterol C-methyltransferase	lipid biosynthesis

Table 3. GO enrichment associated terms with the central nodes in the Proteomics correlated PPI subnetwork.

PCA and PLS correlate epistatic genes with different metabolites

PCA analysis was done to correlate metabolomics and transcriptomics data. The first step was to identify the significant number of components. Figure 9 shows the percentage of variation explained by each component for the two datasets for which we selected two. We found that for the metabolomics dataset the variation explained by the first 2 components is less than the transcriptomics, we think this is due to as metabolites are product of a complex network of gene interactions and protein functions.

We also observed that the PCA for the subset of the epistatic genes changes the structure that we see for the whole transcriptomics dataset. For the epistatic genes the HL mutant and WT are closer, which makes sense since this is a subset made from differentially expressed genes in comparisons using the WT genotype. For the metabolomics we observed a higher variation in the HL and L mutants which indicate that the replicates are not consistent with the measurements, maybe because of experimental limitations or high variability in the compounds.

Figure 9. PCA analysis of transcriptomics and metabolomics datasets. (A-D) Whole transcriptome. (E,F) Epistatic genes.

For the PLS analysis we built a heatmap and variance plots with the correlation within the datasets. Figure 10 shows the results. When we used the whole transcriptome we got more defined clusters that grouped genes and metabolites, however the grouping with the epistatic genes is acceptable, which recovered a very similar structure. We identified three groups of metabolites: one related with nucleotide biosynthesis, a second one with peptide metabolism and a third one with catabolism of sugars.

Conclusions

The analyses presented in the project allowed us to identify a group of candidate epistatic genes and characterize them. We identified regulators associated with them and several structures using protein-protein interaction networks, gene regulatory networks, proteomics and metabolomics data. These genes have a higher correlation at the proteomics level and some clusters have different distribution of degrees in PPI as compared to the whole genome. PCA and PLS showed less reproducibility in the metabolomics dataset and a good explanatory level for the epistatic genes as compared to the whole transcriptome.

References

- Alam, M. T., Zelezniak, A., Mülleder, M., Shliaha, P., Schwarz, R., Capuano, F., ... Ralser, M. (2016). The metabolic background is a global player in *Saccharomyces* gene expression epistasis. *Nature Microbiology*, 1(3), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmicrobiol.2015.30>
- Csardi, G., & Nepusz, T. (2006). The igraph software package for complex network research. *InterJournal, Complex Sy*, 1695.
- Huynh-Thu, V. A., Irrthum, A., Wehenkel, L., & Geurts, P. (2010). Inferring regulatory networks from expression data using tree-based methods. *PLoS ONE*, 5(9), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0012776>
- Love, M. I., Huber, W., & Anders, S. (2014). Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with DESeq2. *Genome Biology*, 15(12), 550. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-014-0550-8>
- Stark, C. (2005). BioGRID: a general repository for interaction datasets. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 34(90001), D535–D539. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkj109>
- Yu, G., Wang, L.-G., Han, Y., & He, Q.-Y. (2012). clusterProfiler: an R Package for Comparing Biological Themes Among Gene Clusters. *OMICS: A Journal of Integrative Biology*, 16(5), 284–287. <https://doi.org/10.1089/omi.2011.0118>